

Research

Chinese and International Green Bond Market: a Comparative Analysis of the Financial Performance Between Green Bonds and Conventional Bonds

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Abstract: *With climate change being the leading problem of our generation, green bonds allow companies to become more environmentally responsible and sustainable; however, there is not enough information on green bond profitability. Research has shown contradictory results, but most studies conclude that green bonds produce lower yields. This research aims to help fill the literature gap by comparing the international and Chinese market, and the performance of green bonds against conventional bonds denominated in euro currency.*

The analysis was carried out on two data samples between 2013 and 2019, applying the Matching method and an extended Fama-French model. Compared to other studies, this research uses the Merton model to calculate the default factor for the Fama-French regressions. The results indicate that conventional bonds outperform green bonds. The research contributes by demonstrating that the default factor calculated with the Merton model is a better fit than the original default premium factor used in the Fama-French regressions.

Keywords: *Green Bonds, Matching Method, Fama-French Model, Fama-MacBeth Regression*

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1. Introduction

A new investment segment, called environmental, social and governance (ESG) criteria, is becoming increasingly popular, as does Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). For asset managers and investors it means investing in companies that choose to tackle the climate change issue. For companies, it means to be more socially accountable and ensuring their actions have a positive impact on the environment, consumers, employees, etc. A good way for a company to raise its finance for low carbon and environment-friendly projects is to issue the so-called “green” bonds.

Green bonds, also called climate bonds, help to encourage sustainability and financially support climate-related environment-friendly projects, for example, projects aimed at energy efficiency, pollution prevention, sustainable agriculture, fishery and forestry, clean transportation, sustainable water management, etc. Green bonds for the international market are defined as any type of bond instrument that is in line with the Green Bond Principles (GBP) and where the use of the proceeds is restricted to financing eco-friendly projects (ICMA, 2018). However, strict regulations or requirements for bonds to be labeled “green” have not yet been agreed upon. It is not clear if a green bond has to be attached to a sustainable environment-friendly project directly, or if it is enough for the bond to just simply back other funds that partly finance projects with an environmentally conscious aim.

China is one of the leading climate bond issuers in the world, but its green bond market is working on different rules and regulations than the international market, that are not recognized internationally. The international market is managed by different social organizations, and forms the regulations from the bottom up, whereas China’s market is managed by the authorities, and the rules are formed in a top-to-down system. The authorities can immediately adapt to the situation at hand and provide better conditions for issuing green bonds, thus ensuring a rapid and continuous development for China’s green bond market. Perhaps the international, and EUR denominated market, which is analyzed in this paper, could learn from the way China is handling the green bond market, to ensure better outcomes and improve the overall situation of the market.

1.1 Background

The green bond market has grown exponentially during the last few years and up to this day (Morgan Stanley Research, 2017). The first green bond was issued in 2007 by the European Investment Bank, however, the market itself was practically non-existent until 2014, when the Green Bond Principles were established, and the Paris Agreement signed in 2015 (Lewis and Birt, 2018). The green bond market amounted to USD 167.3 billion in 2018 (CBI, 2018), yet it attains only 1% of the entire global bond market (Lindberg, 2018). However, the market is expected to continue expanding to reach USD 23 trillion by the year 2030 (IFC, 2018).

As climate change and global warming become evident, and a growing number of people are adapting to a greener lifestyle, there are also more and more companies that are ready to take a step forward and change their work projects and activities to become more environment-friendly and thus be perceived as more sustainable. Since the Paris Agreement on climate change was signed in 2015, Socially Responsible Investments (SRIs) have become a serious topic in financial markets, as the markets are growing and changing to fill the demand for responsible investments. Accordingly, green bonds have become a useful financial tool for firms to take action against climate change, and at the same time be perceived as environment-friendly, sustainable and green.

The US, Europe, and China are the main climate bond issuers in the world (Graph 1). Although the US dominates the market because of a rapid growth in its municipal green bond market, the overall situation suggests that China is the global leader in general green bond issuance. There is a clear demand for climate bonds across developing countries with emerging economies, and since 2017, there is an increasing number of green bond issuances in countries like China, India, Mexico, and others. China's government issues clear guidelines for the green bond issuance. These guidelines could possibly contribute to the international set of policies regarding green bond issuance; however, the regulations set by China's authorities are not recognized by the international market (Weber and Saravade, 2019).

Graph 1. Green Bond Issuance by Countries in Percentage

Source: Weber and Saravade, 2019

1.1.1 International Green Bond Market

As mentioned before, the first green bond was issued in 2007, and in 2008 the World Bank issued another one. At that period, the market was still small and did not have a substantial development during the 2007-2008 financial crisis. In 2013, the market started to grow rapidly, with 11 billion new bonds issued, and this growth continues to this day, with the number of green bonds almost doubling every year, as illustrated in Graph 2. At the moment, there are 321 active bond issues in euro currency, amounting to EUR 164 billion in total. There are 135 green bond issuers in euros, and they vary from sovereign issuers to non-financial institutions. Bonds issued in Belgium and France cover half of the whole euro-denominated green bond market (CBI, 2018). Thus, given the information available and the significant size of the green bond market in EUR, this statistical and analytical research is focused on the euro currency.

Graph 2 demonstrates the development of corporate green bonds from 2012 to 2018, and evidently proves the rapid growth of climate bonds issued during the indicated period of time. The overall volume of green bonds issued in 2013 amounted to USD 11 billion. Currently, there are 1439 active issues, amounting to USD 400 billion in total. This tendency of growth is expected to remain for the upcoming years, particularly, because of the continuous popularity of environment-friendly and sustainable finance. Nonetheless, the actual scope of issuance depends

on which list of green bonds is used. For example, the numbers will change if only the list from CBI or the list from Bloomberg is taken into account (Ehlers and Packer, 2016).

Graph 2. The Growth of Green Bonds

Source: Bloomberg Database

The interest in sustainable and responsible financial investments is continuously increasing, especially after the Paris agreement and Rio Climate Summit (Chatterjee et al., 2016). It is known that new market issues frequently feature oversubscription. At the end of Q2 2017, green bonds were oversubscribed 2.3 times in EUR and 2.8 times in USD market (Harrison, 2018). This high demand for green bonds might lead to lower liquidity risk. Because of the rapid growth of the green bond market, there is a concern that it could just be a phase that will pass; however, analysts predict a continuously stable growth for the green bond market (Morgan Stanley Research, 2017; Christopher, 2017; Allen, 2018). Another sign that the market is maturing, is the minor liquidity risk impact on yield spread (Schafer et al., 2017).

1.1.2 Managing the International and Chinese Markets

Scholars Karpf and Mandel (2017) argue that there is still a poor understanding of what exactly is the meaning of the “green” label. There are indeed many different descriptions of what a green bond actually is. In general, the commonly established fact states that the proceeds from green bonds have to be dedicated to financing environmentally friendly and sustainable projects only (CBI, 2018). However, as mentioned before, there are some organizations that created

criteria to manage the issuance of green bonds. One of the most prevalent international organizations of this kind is the Green Bond Principles (GBP), established by a joint cooperation between the International Capital Markets Association (ICMA) and 13 investment banks¹(Kidney, 2014).The GBP has 4 main principles for marking a bond as “green”:

1. the use of proceeds;
2. project evaluation and selection;
3. management of proceeds;
4. reporting.

While it discusses these principles for climate bond issuance on its own, the GBP also encourages firms to look for an external evaluation for their green project approval. Another example of climate bond regulations is the Climate Bonds Standards, designed by a global investor-focused non-profit organization: the Climate Bond Initiative (CBI). In comparison to the GBP, the CBI uses Climate Bonds Taxonomy, a guide for issuers, investors, governments and municipalities to assist them in understanding what the main investments could be that would provide a reduced carbon economy. The Taxonomy groups climate bonds according to the following 8 categories (CBI, 2018):

1. energy;
2. transport;
3. water;
4. buildings;
5. land use and marine resources;
6. industry;
7. waste;
8. ICT (Information and Communication Technology).

Only those bonds with at least 95% of their proceeds directed to finance environment-friendly projects are allowed to be included in the CBI green bonds database. The database currently has USD 23.5 billion worth of green bonds that match with the CBI standards.

As argued by Huang and Yue (2019), the international market of green bonds operates only on a set of so-called “soft laws” like the GBP and the CBS. When looking from this perspective, China is a special case, because, unlike in the developed countries, China’s green bond market is ruled by “hard laws” that are official legal documents. China’s internal green bond market differs, and thus is not included in the international green bond market. In China,

¹Bank of America Corporation, Citigroup, Crédit Agricole CIB, JPMorgan Chase, BNP Paribas, Daiwa, Deutsche Bank, Goldman Sachs, HSBC, Mizuho, Morgan Stanley, Rabobank and SEB.

the market developed from a different point, and established under a different system; therefore, it does not possess the same rules and does not operate under the same regulations as the international market. In a way, China became a “game-changer” in the green bond market (Bloomberg, 2015).

When comparing the specific regulations and standards for green bond issuance amongst the international market and China’s domestic market, it can be concluded that China’s regulations are mostly consistent with the international ones. In general, there are two differences. One, the proportion of proceeds that is applied to climate bonds differs. According to GBP, PBC and CSRC, at least 95% of the proceeds should be spent with an environment-friendly aim. However, the green bonds that are issued under NDRC guidance, are allowed to give up to 50% of the green bond proceeds to pay back bank loans. Two, the definition and criteria for green projects is different. Some of the categories China has are not included in the GBP and CBI (Huang and Yue, 2019).

1.1.3 Green Bond Market in China

The first green bond issued in China was in 2014 and amounted to CNY 1 billion. One year later, in 2015, the People’s Bank of China (PBC) published the “Announcement on Matters Concerning Issuance of Green Financial Bonds in the Inter-bank Bond Market” (PBC, 2015). In 2016, China had already become the world’s largest green bond market at that time, accounting for 39% of the global green bond issues (CBI and CCDC, 2017).

For the international green bond market, the rules are made from the bottom up, as they are influenced by the investors, stock exchanges and social organizations, whereas for China’s market, the rules are set from top to down, as they are imposed from the leading authorities. In order to understand China’s green bond market, it is necessary to understand where it grew from and the political factors behind it (Huang and Yue, 2019). Table 1 lists the regulatory authorities and their issued documents or “hard laws” for green bond issuance in China.

Table 1. Authorities and their Issued Documents for Green Bond Issuance in China

Year	Issuer	Document
2015	People’s Bank of China (PBC)	Announcement on matters concerning issuance of green financial bonds in the inter-bond market

2015	National Development and Reform Commission (NDRC)	Guidelines on issuance of green bonds
2016	Shanghai Stock Exchange (SSE)	Notice on initiating the pilot program of green corporate bonds
2016	Interotc Co., Ltd (Interotc)	Notice on initiating the pilot program of green bonds
2016	Shenzhen Stock Exchange (SZSE)	Notice on initiating the pilot program of green corporate bonds business
2017	China Securities Regulatory Commission (CSRC)	Guiding opinions on supporting the development of green bonds
2017	National Association of Financial Market Institutional Investors (NAFMII)	Guidelines for Green Debt Financing Instruments of Non-Financial Enterprises

Source: Huang and Yue, 2019

As stated by Article 80 of the Legislation Law of the People’s Republic of China, the NDRC, the PBC, and the CSRC may frame the green bond issuance regulations within their power. The Interotc and the NAFMII are under the PBC control and have only supervisory command in the market. Nonetheless, the regulations they issue are accepted by the PBC. THE SSE and SZSE are also under government supervision, meaning, they need CSRC’s approval; however, their issued regulations are guaranteed by Article 118 of China’s Securities law.

With the distinctive system and unique rules, China has achieved rapid growth in its newly established green bond market. The legal documents mention objectives such as: providing easy access to the green bond market, improving the efficiency of listing and transfer, increasing the convenience of climate bond issuance, thus ensuring an ongoing development for the market. With these favorable objectives coming from the authorities, the review period for green bond issuance is way shorter than the issuance period for other financing processes in China (Huang and Yue, 2019).

In general, the current development of China’s climate bond market is influenced by a variety of its economic, political and legal factors. These factors combined developed the distinct “hard laws” that China possesses, whereas the international market is seen to have “soft laws” for green bond issuance.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 The Matching Method

The data used for the Matching Method was retrieved from Bloomberg's fixed income database and consists of 327 green bonds from 15 different countries, issued by 45 different companies. The keywords written to search for the data were "use of proceeds". Only bonds that met the requirements of the Green Bond Principles (GBP) were picked, meaning, bonds searched were filtered by "green bond" and "green loan" labels, this way eliminating green bonds that were falsely categorized by the issuer or lacked this data. Those bonds were taken as regular conventional bonds or non-investment grade bonds and thus were excluded from the green bond dataset.

The dataset consists of 5000 corporate bonds in total, issued from 2013 to 2019. The year 2013 is chosen as the initial point, as it was the time when green bonds started to become more popular and issued at faster rates. In this research, it is assumed that all coupon payments are reinvested at the computed yield to maturity (YTM) rate. The complete dataset has a mean maturity rate of 7.1 years for green bonds, and 7.3 years for synthetic conventional bonds, making sure the data is matched adequately and is suitable for answering the main research question. All of the bonds used in this research are EUR denominated. The average YTM is 0.343 for green bonds, and 0.341 for traditional conventional bonds. The standard deviation is 0.531 for green bonds, and 0.529 for conventional bonds.

To evaluate the yield difference between the two types of bonds, a compatible database of green and conventional bonds in EUR was made for the purpose of this research. The entire sample of GBP verified 327 corporate green bonds were examined. To decrease maturity bias, each climate bond was matched with a synthetic conventional bond, and the two bonds were searched with the closest maturity. Next, the bond issue date difference was limited to six years earlier or later at most. These limitations were made to control the liquidity bias when estimating the green bond premium. Furthermore, the bond data from Bloomberg and Datastream was gathered in relation to issue amount, currency, maturity, coupon, Moody's credit rating and yield to maturity median. All of the aforementioned criteria are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. The Matching Criteria

Characteristic	Matching Criteria
Issuer	Precise match
Issue date	± 6 years

Maturity date	± 2 years
Payment security	Precise match
Moody's rating	Precise match

2.2 The Fama-French Method

The data used for the extended Fama-French model analysis was retrieved from Bloomberg's fixed income database and consists of 46 active green bonds from 21 different countries, issued by 36 different companies. The keywords written to search for the data were "use of proceeds", and, the same as for the Matching Method, only bonds that fit "green bond" and "green loan" labels, were picked.

The dataset consists of 5000 corporate bonds in total, issued from 2013 to 2015. This time period was chosen to make emphasis on the start of the green bond "boom" (Graph 2). By choosing this specific period, it was ensured that all of the relevant metrics information on the bonds will be found, thus excluding the possibility of inaccuracies in the analysis related to missing variables. Additionally, 86 active conventional bonds were chosen by the same criteria as in section 3.1. Thus the final sample used in the extended Fama-French model has 132 active bonds in total.

Although in the original Fama and French (1993) paper the dataset is divided into 7 portfolios, in this research the dataset is divided into 14 equally weighted industry portfolios, the same as in studies done by Johansson et al. (2012), Piva (2017) and Flammer (2018). This division is chosen considering the time period and sample size.

2.2.1 Fama-MacBeth Regression

For more accurate and better results, the Fama-MacBeth regression method was applied. Because Fama-MacBeth regression only corrects for cross-sectional correlation, to correct autocorrelation, the Newey-West estimator was used to estimate standard errors as recommended by Petersen (2009).

To apply the Fama-MacBeth approach to this research, first, separate 6-factor time-series regressions of average monthly excess returns for each company's portfolio were made. It was done to estimate the factor loadings used later in the analysis. The equation for the first step is as follows (Equation 1):

$$r_{it} - r_{ft} = \alpha_{i,t} + \beta_{i,r_M-r_f}[r_{Mt} - r_{ft}] + \beta_{i,SMB}SMB_t + \beta_{i,HML}HML_t + \beta_{i,MOM}MOM_t + \beta_{i,TERM}TERM_t + \beta_{i,PD}PD_t + u_{it} \quad (1)$$

Second, the average excess bond returns were regressed against the lambda coefficients (λ) of the factor loadings gotten from Equation 1. A dummy variable ($GREEN_i$) was added, having value 1 for green bonds and value 0 for conventional bonds. λ_{GREEN} measures the outcome of a conventional bond being “green”. The regressions were done using a bi-annual rolling window regression approach. The equation for the second step is as follows (Equation 2):

$$r_i - r_t = \lambda_0 + \lambda_{r_M-r_f}\beta_{i,r_M-r_f} + \lambda_{SMB}\beta_{i,SMB} + \lambda_{HML}\beta_{i,HML} + \lambda_{MOM}\beta_{i,MOM} + \lambda_{TERM}\beta_{i,TERM} + \lambda_{PD}\beta_{i,PD} + \lambda_{GREEN}GREEN_i + u_{it} \quad (2)$$

3. Analysis and Results

3.1 The Matching Method

First, the nearest neighbor matching with replacement method is used to equate the distribution of covariates in treated (green bonds) and control (conventional bonds) groups. The results were computed with the following equation (Equation 3):

$$Yield\ difference = Y^{GB} - Y^{CB} \quad (3)$$

The matching was done by the criteria described in Table 1. After matching, the sample contained 70 green bonds, matched with 70 synthetic bonds. If any green bond had less than 2 matching conventional bonds, it was not taken into account and excluded. The paired t-test was done 3 times, once for the whole sample, and then separately for the 2 sub-samples. The first sub-sample was made of bonds issued from 2013 to 2015, and the second sub-sample was made of bonds issued from 2016 to 2019. For all 3 tests, the null hypo of the mean difference was rejected as being equal to zero at a 1% significance level. The results are described in the table below (Table 3):

Table 3. The Matching Method Results.

	Yield difference (whole sample)	Yield difference (2013-2015 sample)	Yield difference (2016-2019 sample)
Mean	0.0072***	-0.0433***	0.0247***
Standard Error	0.0201	0.0287	0.0249
Median	0.0010	-0.0303	0.0282
Mode	N/A	N/A	N/A
Standard Deviation	0.1684	0.1217	0.1795
Sample Variance	0.0284	0.0148	0.0322

Kurtosis	0.6790	2.0470	0.5842
Skewness	0.0866	0.5312	-0.1154
Range	0.9088	0.5413	0.9088
Minimum	-0.4384	-0.2646	-0.4384
Maximum	0.4705	0.2767	0.4705
Sum	0.5039	-0.7787	1.2827
Count	70	18	52

Significance markers: * for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$, *** for $p < 0.01$

The results are divided into two sub-samples, years 2013-2015 and years 2016-2019 respectively. This division was chosen to obtain a clearer observation of the green bond “boom” period (2013-2015), and the more recent years. Both of the samples have a yield difference that is significant to a 1% level. It is noteworthy that the yield difference for the green bond sub-sample of 2013-2015 is negative. Nevertheless, the sub-sample is consistent and compatible with the results of the Fama-French method.

The results on average reveal a 72bps (0.72%) higher yield for green bonds than the otherwise equal conventional bonds. The result is significant at a 1% level, and also coincides with the results achieved by VanEck (2017), Karpf and Mandel (2018) and Bos et al. (2018), who all found a positive yield difference for green bonds. VanEck debates that such a situation could be possible only in markets expressing a high demand for environmental-friendly projects, like Europe.

For further examination, the results are divided into 3 other sub-samples: year of the issue, country of the issue and credit rating.

First, when dividing the results by the year of issue, it can be observed that the green bond premium exists in the green bonds issued in years 2013, 2016 and 2018 (Table 4). The presence of the premium changes almost every other year, which could be a sign of an imbalance in the supply and demand of green bonds. Also, although the signs change, the yield difference becomes closer to zero for the bonds that are issued in the more recent years, that is, 2016-2019. Except for years 2013 and 2019, all of the other year yield differences for green bonds are significant. The reason why the years 2013 and 2019 present an insignificant result could be explained by the small sample size these years offer.

Table 4. Average Yield Difference by the Year of Issue.

Year	Average Yield Difference
2013	0.1353
2014	-0.0820***
2015	-0.0581***
2016	0.0394***
2017	-0.0255***
2018	0.0883***
2019	-0.0077

Significance markers: * for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$, *** for $p < 0.01$

Further, the results are divided by the country of issue. The results reveal that the yield premium is positive in some countries, and negative in other countries (Table 4). For Belgium, Finland, Norway, and Portugal the result is insignificant due to the small sample size. For countries like Finland, France, Norway and Sweden, the results coincide with the results obtained by Bos et al. (2018), who found that the green bonds issued in Finland have a positive yield difference, while it is negative for the green bonds issued in Norway, and that the yield difference for green bonds issued in France and Sweden is close to zero. Nevertheless, for countries like Germany, Italy, and Spain, the results are opposite as the ones obtained by Bos et al. The results these scholars obtained reveal a positive yield difference for the green bonds issued in Germany and Italy, but a negative yield difference for the green bonds issued in Spain. This inconsistency in results could be explained by the different data samples used in both types of research. This analyzes only EUR currency-denominated corporate issues, whereas Bos et al. analyze the bonds denominated in each country's individual currency.

Table 5. Average Yield Difference by the Country of Issue.

Country of Issue	Average Yield Difference
Australia	0.2649**
Belgium	0.1228
Denmark	0.1148*
Finland	0.0643
France	-0.0091***
Germany	-0.0072***
Italy	-0.0141**
Japan	0.1602***
Luxembourg	-0.1203***
Norway	-0.0585
The Netherlands	0.0261***

The United Kingdom	-0.3189***
Portugal	-0.155
Spain	0.1294***
Sweden	0.0025**

Significance markers: * for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$, *** for $p < 0.01$

Lastly, the average yield spread is compared across the issuer's credit rating. The results reveal that for Aaa, Aa2, A2, Baa1 and Baa2 rating, the green bond premium is close to zero, where for A3 and Baa3 rated bonds the premium is significantly negative (Table 6). For Aaa, A2 and Baa2 ratings, the results coincide with the research done by Zerbib (2019), who found that the yield difference is negative for the Aaa rating, but positive for A2 and Baa2 rating. However, the results do not match with Zerbib for negative premium in Aa2, A2 and Baa2 rated bonds. As Bos et al. (2018) have already expressed, there seems to be no evident connection between credit rating and yield differential. For ratings Aaa, Aa1, A2, A3 and Baa2, the sign for the average yield difference coincides with the research done by Bos et al.

Table 6. Average Yield Difference by Credit Rating.

Credit Rating	Average Yield Difference
Aaa	-0.0248***
Aa1	-0.1003**
Aa2	0.0025**
Aa3	0.1033***
A1	0.0555***
A2	0.0354
A3	-0.3504
Baa1	0.0263***
Baa2	0.0015
Baa3	-0.2212**
N/A	-0.0212**

Significance markers: * for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$, *** for $p < 0.01$

3.1.1 The Robustness Test

The robustness test was done to validate the results from the Matching method, as stricter criteria were introduced. Now, the matching was done by narrowing the bond issue date from 6 to 1 year or less. All the other criteria (issuer, credit rating, seniority, and maturity) were held the

same as before (Table 1). Thus the new sample for the robustness test consisted of 44 pairs, whereas the original sample consisted of 70 pairs.

It is interesting to note that the results obtained from the robustness test were completely opposite as the results obtained from the Matching method, where the criteria were not as strict (Table 7). Performing the robustness test, the yield difference between green and conventional bonds was -196bps (-1.96%), indicating that the yield of green bonds was lower. This result matches the result attained from the Fama-French method. Additionally, the paired t-test was conducted. The mean yield difference between green and conventional bonds was significant at a 1% level in all three samples.

Table 7. Robustness Test Results.

	Robustness test (whole sample)	Robustness test (2013-2015 sample)	Robustness test (2016-2019 sample)
Mean	-0.0196***	-0.0380***	-0.0149***
Standard Error	0.0278	0.0526	0.0325
Median	-0.0003	-0.0134	0.0029
Mode	N/A	N/A	N/A
Standard Deviation	0.1842	0.1579	0.1921
Sample Variance	0.0339	0.0249	0.0369
Kurtosis	2.6650	1.6079	3.0109
Skewness	-1.0310	0.4450	-1.2402
Range	1.0006	0.5497	1.0006
Minimum	-0.6547	-0.2730	-0.6547
Maximum	0.3459	0.2767	0.3459
Sum	-0.8617	-0.3417	-0.5201
Count	44	9	35

Significance markers: * for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$, *** for $p < 0.01$

Taken that stricter criteria were applied, the newly obtained results should be more accurate, as the maturity bias or other features that could have affected the yield, were isolated. Also, these results were consistent with the majority of previous literature showing a lower yield for green bonds, like Preclaw and Bakshi (2015), Ehlers and Packer (2017), Wurgler et al. (2018), Zerbib (2019).

3.2 The Fama-French Model with PD Factor

When running the Fama-MacBeth regressions, in the first step, the Real Estate industry suggested autocorrelation, explicitly in the 2nd, 3rd, and 5th lags. After correcting the time-series

regression for the Real Estate industry, all of the factor coefficients became more significant. The most significant, at a 10% level, was the PD factor, and at a 5% level, the RM-RF factor. Besides, during the first step, the Manufacturing and Construction industries showed heteroscedasticity. After correcting the regressions using the Newey-West estimator, the PD factor for Manufacturing became significant at a 10% level, and the TERM factor for the Construction industry became significant at a 5% level.

During the second step of the Fama-MacBeth regression, heteroscedasticity was found in 4 cross-sectional regressions: the 1st, 3rd, 4th, and 5th rolling window regression sub-periods. After correcting the regression with the Newey-West estimator, the TERM and SMB factors remained insignificant, the MOM factor became significant at a 10% level, and the other factors became significant at a 5% level for the 1st sub-period (1/2016-6/2016). For the 3rd sub-period (1/2017-6/2017), after corrections, the SMB factor became less significant, while the other factors became slightly more significant. For the 4th sub-period (7/2017-12/2017), the SMB factor became less significant, the MOM factor became significant at a 10% level, while the other factors became slightly more significant. For the 5th sub-period (1/2018-6/2018), the HML factor became significant at a 10% level, while the other factors became slightly more significant.

The dummy variable “GREEN” (λ GREEN) was significant at a 1% level for the 1st, 3rd and 6th sub-periods and significant at a 10% level for the 5th sub-period (Table 8). On average, the dummy variable has a negative coefficient (-0.063), from which it can be concluded that traditional conventional bonds perform better than green bonds over the given sample period, which corresponded with the robustness test conducted for the Matching method.

Table 8. Dummy Variable “GREEN” for the PD Factor.

Sub-period	λ GREEN
1/2016-6/2016	-0.1956*** (0.0526)
7/2016-12/2016	0.0061 (0.0083)
1/2017-6/2017	0.0217*** (0.0044)
7/2016-12/2017	-0.0064 (0.0062)
1/2018-6/2018	-0.0665* (0.0382)
7/2018-12/2018	-0.0932***

	(0.0270)
1/2019-4/2019	-0.1189 (0.1310)
Average Coefficient	-0.063

Significance markers: * for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$, *** for $p < 0.01$

Standard errors in parentheses.

3.3 Robustness Test with the DEF Factor

As defined by Fama and French (1993), the default factor DEF is the difference between the return on a market portfolio of long-term corporate bonds and long-term government bonds. The robustness test was done for the DEF factor instead of the credit rating because the DEF factor captures the time-varying default risk of bonds, while the credit rating might not properly reflect the recent information and thus give an inaccurate proxy for a bond's default risk (Bystrom, 2006). Thus the robustness test was done with the DEF factor instead of the PD factor. The calculations were done using the Bloomberg European Corporate Investment Grade Index as a proxy for the long-term government bond return and the monthly Germany 10 year bond yield. The $\beta_{i,DEF}$ coefficient measures the effect of default probability on bond return. The two equations used for the robustness test with the DEF factor were as follows:

$$r_{it} - r_{ft} = \alpha_{i,t} + \beta_{i,r_M-r_f} [r_{Mt} - r_{ft}] + \beta_{i,SMB} SMB_t + \beta_{i,HML} HML_t + \beta_{i,MOM} MOM_t + \beta_{i,TERM} TERM_t + \beta_{i,DEF} DEF_t + u_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

$$r_i - r_f = \lambda_0 + \lambda_{r_M-r_f} \beta_{i,r_M-r_f} + \lambda_{SMB} \beta_{i,SMB} + \lambda_{HML} \beta_{i,HML} + \lambda_{MOM} \beta_{i,MOM} + \lambda_{TERM} \beta_{i,TERM} + \lambda_{DEF} \beta_{i,DEF} + \lambda_{GREEN} GREEN_i + u_i \quad (2)$$

Similarly as before, the regression indicated signs of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity, thus they were corrected using the Newey-West (1987) estimator.

In the first step of the regression, Energy and Utilities industries showed autocorrelation. After the correction for the Energy industry time-series regression, the HML factor became significant at a 5% level, while for the Utilities industry, all of the regression factors became slightly more significant, the SMB factor became significant at a 10% level, and the HML factor became significant at a 5% level.

Heteroscedasticity was present for the Energy and Manufacturing industries. After the corrections were made for the Energy industry, the HML factor became significant at a 5% level, while the other factors stayed insignificant. For the Manufacturing industry, all the factors became more significant, except for the HML factor which became less significant, although still remained significant at a 5% level, and the SMB factor, which stayed significant at a 10% level.

In the second step of the regression, using the DEF factor, heteroscedasticity showed for the 1st, 3rd, 4th, and 5th rolling window sub-periods. After the correction with the Newey-West estimator, the SMB and TERM factors became significant at a 10% level, and the DEF factor became significant at a 5% level for the 1st sub-period. For the 3rd sub-period, only the RM-RF factor was significant at a 5% level. As for the 4th sub-period, only the DEF factor became more significant at a 10% level. And for the 5th sub-period, all of the factors remained insignificant.

The results for the robustness test for the Fama-French model with the DEF factor indicated the dummy variable GREEN significant at a 1% level for the 3rd and 6th sub-periods, and significant a 5% level for the 1st sub-period. As already seen with the PD factor earlier, also now the Green dummy variable showed a negative coefficient -0.068, indicating that, for the given period, conventional bonds perform better than green bonds (Table 9).

Table 9. Dummy Variable “GREEN” for the DEF Factor.

Sub-period	λ GREEN
1/2016-6/2016	-0.2339** (0.0912)
7/2016-12/2016	0.0047 (0.0077)
1/2017-6/2017	0.0219*** (0.0042)
7/2016-12/2017	0.0041 (0.0058)
1/2018-6/2018	-0.0641 (0.0407)
7/2018-12/2018	-0.0930*** (0.0271)
1/2019-4/2019	-0.1155 (0.1240)
Average Coefficient	-0.068

Significance markers: * for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$, *** for $p < 0.01$

Standard errors in parentheses.

3.4 Comparison between PD and DEF Results

When comparing the results obtained from the use of the PD factor and the DEF factor, it is clear that the outcomes are more significant when the PD is used as the default factor. Thus it can be concluded that the Merton model is a better and more accurate method for calculating the probability of default than the DEF factor in the Fama-French method.

It is noteworthy that the data samples for the Matching method and Fama-French method differed with the chosen periods of time for each sample. For the Matching method, the sample consisted of bonds issued between 2013 to 2019, while for the Fama-French method, the sample consisted of bonds issued between 2016 to 2019. Because of this difference, the results cannot be compared directly. Moreover, the main results between the two methods did not match, however, the Fama-French results matched with the robustness test of the Matching method, which was done with stricter criteria. Because of this, it can be said that the result of the robustness test for the Matching method was a better reflection of the Fama-French result, and thus it can be concluded that conventional bonds perform better than green bonds.

Other trends that can be read from the analysis exhibit heteroscedasticity for the Manufacturing industry both in the main and robustness test. Also, autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity are present for the Energy industry when the DEF factor is used. Furthermore, the dummy variable GREEN was significant at a 5% level for the 1st, 3rd, and 6th sub-periods both for in the main and robustness test.

The results obtained in this research coincide with the research done by Zerbib (2019), who concluded that conventional bonds outperform green bonds in the period of 2013 to 2017. He also found a negative premium, as is done in this research; however, there are differences when it comes to methods used and the green bonds chosen for the study. Zerbib used only the Matching method, while in this research both the Matching method and the Fama-French method were used. Moreover, Zerbib used green bonds denominated in any currency, while here the bonds used were only denominated in EUR currency. As well, Zerbib's green bond yield difference was about 18 bps, whereas in this it was 72 bps. Therefore it is interesting to observe that the final result complies, even though the samples of the two studies were different.

Overall, the results from the Fama-French method presented a low significance for all the given factors, except for the year 2013, which was the period for the so-called green bond "boom". This was also observed by Wagner (2017), who also used the Fama-French method in

his study. Even though Wagner did not point the low significance to any specific factors, it could be explained by the unbalanced data sample, which, as mentioned before, was also one of the limitations of this study.

In general, it was problematic to make a comparison for the Fama-French results obtained in this study, because of the limited amount of other studies that use the Fama-French method for analyzing returns on corporate bonds. In conclusion, the results are inconsistent and contradictory with the other similar studies made. This confirms the assumption made before about the results of studies on the performance of the green bonds compared to conventional bonds being inconclusive.

4. Conclusion

The objective of this research was to compare the difference in performance for green bonds and conventional bonds denominated in EUR currency and to see if there are areas where the euro-denominated green bond market could improve with adapting China's green bond market regulations. The data for comparing green bonds and conventional bonds was collected following the Bloomberg Green Bond label, with the use of proceeds indicated for environmental-friendly projects. The sample size contained 70 green bonds issued from the year 2013 to the year 2019 that were matched with 124 conventional bonds that had the same features. The starting point of the sample period, the year 2013, was chosen because it was the beginning of the so-called green bond "boom" when the number of green bonds in the market started to skyrocket and grew at an exponential rate.

To isolate the influence of other factors like credit rating, maturity, seniority, issuer, and compute the difference in yield for the treated and control group, the Matching method was used. According to the results obtained, on average, green bonds had a higher yield when compared to conventional bonds; furthermore, the yield spread was tighter and became positive for the 2016-2019 year sub-sample. This finding leads to propose that green bonds issued during the green bond boom period pay a higher yield than the bonds issued from 2016 to 2019.

Next, for additional testing, the bonds were divided into 14 portfolios by the industry of the issuer. Following the Fama-MacBeth method, time-series regression was run with five of the Fama-French factors, Carhart's momentum factor and time-varying, issuer-specific Merton model's PD factor. The coefficients from the time-series regressions were added into the cross-

sectional regressions. The cross-sectional regressions were run for each of the 6-month long sub-periods. Additionally, a robustness test was done, where the same method was used, but the PD factor was substituted by a default factor DEF, as suggested by Fama and French (1993). The results obtained indicated that green bonds on average had a lower yield than conventional bonds. These results coincided with the previous literature found on this topic.

Looking at the Chinese market of green bonds, and analyzing the differences between the Chinese and international markets, it was discovered that there are some differences in how the markets are managed. Where the international market has a bottom to up regulation system and it possesses so-called “soft laws”, the Chinese market is regulated from top to bottom and possesses so-called “hard laws”. Because the international market encounters some management and regulation problems, it could be said that it would be beneficial to take an example from the Chinese market, make stricter regulations and laws for green bond issuance. This could result in the overall development of the international market, as the whole process would be more systematic and transparent for both investors and also the companies issuing bonds. It could lead to even more climate bond issues and bigger investments for environment-friendly and sustainable projects.

All in all, the results of the comparison between two types of bonds in euro currency conclude that being green and environment-friendly leads to less risk for debt and lower yields for investors. The considerably high demand for green bonds proposes that the market is maturing and will continue to grow and develop further. As the outcome of the Matching method for the main sample of the green bonds indicated, the green bonds issued from 2013 to 2015 had a lower yield than the conventional bonds. However, the yield spread between the green and conventional bonds got smaller, and for the bonds issued from 2016 to 2019, it turned positive. The results obtained coincide with the ones achieved by Johansson et al. (2012) and Wagner (2017). In their studies, just as in this research, the Fama-French factors do not display a statistical significance at all times, even after the factors were corrected with the Newey-West estimator. Especially, the default factor did not appear to be a suitable fit for this model, and thus it could be implied that for the Fama-French model, the Merton model is a better estimator for default.

There are a few limitations to this study that were discovered during the research. First, the green bonds market is relatively new, and thus the number of the green bonds issued is small,

especially when compared to the standard conventional bonds. This limits the size of the data sample obtained. Other researchers (Wagner, 2017; Drage and Stundt, 2018; Zerbib, 2019) have also mentioned this as one of the limitations in their studies on green bonds. Second, a great number of green bond issuers are private companies, thus making it difficult to obtain potentially useful information to further improve this research. Third, the bonds in the data sample used in this research might have a lower yield, as the issuers of the bonds tend to be rated higher, with only a small portion rated below investment grade (Ehlers and Packer, 2017). Investment-grade bonds are mostly less risky by standard and thus usually have a lower yield. Deriving from this, it could be said that the bonds that were used in this research have a lower yield and this serves as bias and limitation for this research. Fourth, because, based on previous literature, it was assumed that green bonds work just as good as conventional bonds and that there is a non-negative relationship between green bonds and returns, it also could serve as a limitation to the study.

The studies done on green bonds are still not extensive enough, and future research is needed. It could be suggested to do a deeper analysis on the Chinese green bond market, and then carry out a suitable comparison between the Chinese and the international market, to see in which areas there is a room for improvement. It will be interesting to see if the two markets will come to agreements for one set of regulations, or if one of the sides will adopt the other side's principles. It could also be suggested doing more in-depth research on the companies issuing green bonds and the development of their stock price. Another area worth exploring could be how the fear of possible economic recession would impact investments on green bonds. It will be interesting to see how the green bond market will develop in the upcoming years and decades, and whether it will truly be a growing market, or turn out to be just a trend that will slowly start to fade with time. Also, it will be exciting to see in which direction the bond yield spread will turn in the future.

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